

Article

Establishment of Kifilideen coefficient tables for positive and negative powers of n and $-n$ of Kifilideen trinomial theorem and other development based on matrix and standardized methods

Kifilideen L. Osanyinpeju

¹ Agricultural and Bio-Resources Engineering Department, College of Engineering, Federal University of Agriculture Abeokuta, Ogun State.

* Correspondence: amkifilideenosanyinpeju@gmail.com, prof_4us@yahoo.com

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Abstract: The generation of coefficients of terms of positive and negative powers of n and $-n$ of Kifilideen trinomial theorem as the terms are progress is stressful and time-consuming which the same problem is identified with coefficients of terms of binomial theorem of positive and negative powers of n and $-n$. This slows the process of producing the series of any particular trinomial expansion. This study established Kifilideen coefficient tables for positive and negative powers of n and $-n$ of the Kifilideen trinomial theorem and other developments based on matrix and standardized methods. A Kifilideen theorem of matrix transformation of the positive power of n of trinomial expression in which three variables x , y , and z are found in parts of the trinomial expression was originated. The development would ease evaluating the trinomial expression's positive power of n . The Kifilideen coefficient tables are handy and effective in generating the coefficients of terms and series of the Kifilideen expansion of trinomial expression of positive and negative powers of n and $-n$.

Keywords: Coefficients tables; Combination; Kifilideen matrix; Positive and negative powers; Kifilideen expansion.

MSC: 28A20, 60A05.

1. Introduction

Goss [1] and Aljohani [2] indicate that the Binomial theorem for negative and fraction powers of $-n$ and $\frac{a}{b}$ were developed by Sir Isaac Newton (1642 – 1727) in 1665. Bombelli (1572) gave the coefficients of the binomial expansion of $(a + b)^n$ for $n = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, 7$ and Oughtred (1631) provided them for $n = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots, 10$ [3–5]. Blaise Pascal (1623 - 1662), a French mathematician, developed the Pascal triangle, also known as the Yanghui triangle, in 1664 to generate the coefficient of terms of the positive power of binomial theorem [6–10]. Although, from the triangle, there is no indication of how the coefficients are progressing from one term to the other. However, from the binomial theorem expansion, it could be deduced which term owns the coefficient in the Pascal triangle. No publication is available for coefficients of negative power of $-n$ either in triangle form or any other form. This delays the process of generating the series of the binomial theorem involving the negative power of $-n$.

A theorem of Kifilideen matrix transformation of the positive power of n of trinomial expression in which three variables x , y , and z are found in parts of the trinomial expression was originated. The development would ease evaluating the trinomial expression's positive power of n .

Kifilideen (2020) developed the Kifilideen trinomial theorem of the positive power of n for the expansion of the form $[x + y + z]^n$ using the matrix approach, which helps in arranging the terms of the expansion in an orderly and standardized manner and ways [11]. It was observed that the process of generating the coefficient of each term of the expansion of positive and negative powers of n and $-n$ of the trinomial theorem is stressful and time-consuming which the same problem is identified with coefficients of terms of a binomial theorem of powers of n and $-n$ [12,13]. This slows the process of producing the series of any particular trinomial expansion.

Table 1. Pascal coefficient table for terms of series of expansion of positive power of n of Newton’s binomial theorem

Positive power of n																					
Terms	$n=1$	$n=2$	$n=3$	$n=4$	$n=5$	$n=6$	$n=7$	$n=8$	$n=9$	$n=10$	$n=11$	$n=12$	$n=13$	$n=14$	$n=15$	$n=16$	$n=17$	$n=18$	$n=19$		
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19		
3		1	3	6	10	15	21	28	36	45	55	66	78	91	105	120	136	153	171		
4			1	4	10	20	35	56	84	120	165	220	286	364	455	560	680	816	969		
5				1	5	15	35	70	126	210	330	495	715	1001	1365	1820	2380	3060	3876		
6					1	6	21	56	126	252	462	792	1287	2002	3003	4368	6188	8568	11628		
7						1	7	28	84	210	462	924	1716	3003	5005	8008	12376	18564	27132		
8							1	8	36	120	330	792	1716	3432	6435	11440	19448	31824	50388		
9								1	9	45	165	495	1287	3003	6435	12870	24310	43758	75582		
10									1	10	55	220	715	2002	5005	11440	24310	48620	92378		
11										1	11	66	286	1001	3003	8008	19448	43758	92378		
12											1	12	78	364	1365	4368	12376	31824	75582		
13												1	13	91	455	1820	6188	18564	50388		
14													1	14	105	560	2380	8568	27132		
15															1	15	120	680	3060	11628	
16																1	16	136	816	3876	
17																	1	17	153	969	
18																		1	18	171	
19																			1	19	
20																				1	

The establishment of tables of coefficients of positive and negative powers of binomial and trinomial theorems would help and be handy in generating the coefficient of each term of a series and result in easy expansion. In the Tables, each term and its corresponding coefficient will be indicated and linked together. Also, it would show how the coefficients are progressing from one term to the other. This will remove the stress that is been encountered in the expansion process if the Tables are fully utilized. It can serve as a guide and would also help in easy visualization of patterns and analysis in which the coefficients are progressing for each power of n of the binomial and trinomial theorems. Kifilideen matrix approach had been used to evaluate and compute the power of base of eleven, other bi-digits, and tri-digit numbers [14–18]. This study established Kifilideen coefficient tables for positive and negative powers of n and $-n$ for the Kifilideen trinomial theorem.

2. 2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Pascal coefficient table for terms of series of expansion of positive power of n of Newton’s binomial theorem

Table 1 indicates Pascal coefficient table for terms of series of expansion of positive power of n of Newton’s binomial theorem. The series of the terms of Newton’s binomial theorem for a particular positive power of n is finite.

2.2. Kifilideen coefficient table for negative power of $-n$ of Newton’s binomial theorem

Table 2 shows Kifilideen coefficient table for negative power of $-n$ of Newton’s binomial theorem. The series of Newton’s expansion of negative power of $-n$ of binomial theorem gives infinite series which can be shown in the Table below. The series of the terms of Newton’s binomial theorem for a particular negative power of n is infinite.

2.3. Kifilideen power combination table of the terms of the series of Kifilideen expansion of positive power of n of trinomial expression $(x + y + z)$ in a standardized order

Table 3 presents the Kifilideen power combination table of the terms of the series of Kifilideen expansion of positive power of n of trinomial expression $(x + y + z)$ in a standardized order. Each degree of the positive power of n of the Kifilideen expansion of the Kifilideen trinomial theorem has a finite power combination in the series.

2.4. Kifilideen coefficient table for positive power of n of Kifilideen trinomial theorem

Table 4 presents the Kifilideen coefficient table for positive power of n of Kifilideen trinomial theorem based on matrix approach. The series of Kifilideen expansion of positive power of n of trinomial theorem gives finite series which can be shown in the Table below. From the Table 4; the change in colour from blue to red then to blue and so on till the last term for any particular positive power of n indicates the migration

Table 2. The Kifilideen coefficient table for negative power of $-n$ of Newton’s binomial theorem

Negative power of $-n$												
Terms	$n = -1$	$n = -2$	$n = -3$	$n = -4$	$n = -5$	$n = -6$	$n = -7$	$n = -8$	$n = -9$	$n = -10$	$n = -11$	$n = -12$
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
2	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12
3	1	3	6	10	15	21	28	36	45	55	66	78
4	-1	-4	-10	-20	-35	-56	-84	-120	-165	-220	-286	-364
5	1	5	15	35	70	126	210	330	495	715	1001	1365
6	-1	-6	-21	-56	-126	-252	-462	-792	-1287	-2002	-3003	-4368
7	1	7	28	84	210	462	924	1716	3003	5005	8008	12376
8	-1	-8	-36	-120	-330	-792	-1716	-3432	-6435	-11440	-19448	-31824
9	1	9	45	165	495	1287	3003	6435	12870	24310	43758	75582
10	-1	-10	-55	-220	-715	-2002	-5005	-11440	-24310	-48620	-92378	-167960
11	1	11	66	286	1001	3003	8008	19448	43758	92378	184756	352716
12	-1	-12	-78	-364	-1365	-4368	-12376	-31824	-75582	-167960	-352716	-750432
13	1	13	91	455	1820	6188	18564	50388	125970	293930	646646	1352078
14	-1	-14	-105	-560	-2380	-8568	-27132	-77520	-203490	-497420	-1144066	-2496144
15	1	15	120	680	3060	11628	38760	116280	319770	817190	1961256	4457400
16	-1	-16	-136	-816	-3876	-15504	-54264	-170544	-490314	-1307504	-3268760	-7726160
17	1	17	153	969	4845	20349	74613	245157	735471	2042975	5311735	13037895
18	-1	-18	-171	-1140	-5985	-26334	-100947	-346104	-1081575	-3124550	-8436285	-21474180
19	1	19	190	1330	7315	33649	134596	480700	1562275	4686825	13123110	34597290
20	-1	-20	-210	-1540	-8855	-42504	-177100	-657800	-2220075	-6906900	-20030010	-54627300
21	1	21	231	1771	10626	53130	230230	888030	3108105	10015005	30045015	84672315
22	-1	-22	-253	-2024	-12650	-65780	-296010	-1184040	-4292145	-14307150	-44352165	-129024480
23	1	23	276	2300	14950	80730	376740	1560780	5852925	20160075	64512240	193536720
24	-1	-24	-300	-2600	-17550	-98280	-475020	-2035800	-7888725	-28048800	-92561040	-286097760
25	1	25	325	2925	20475	118755	593775	2629575	10518300	38567100	131128140	417225900
26	-1	-26	-351	-3276	-23751	-142506	-736281	-3365856	-13884156	-52451256	-183579396	-600805296
27	1	27	378	3654	27405	169911	906192	4272048	18156204	70607460	254186856	854992152
28	-1	-28	-406	-4060	-31465	-201376	-1107568	-5379616	-23535820	-94143280	-348330136	-1203322288
29	1	29	435	4495	35960	237336	1344904	6724520	30260340	124403620	472733756	1676056044
30	-1	-30	-465	-4960	-40920	-278256	-1623160	-8347680	-38608020	-163011640	-635745396	-2311801440
31	1	31	496	5456	46376	324632	1947792	10295472	48903492	211915132	847660528	3159461968
32	-1	-32	-528	-5984	-52360	-376992	-2324784	-12620256	-61523748	-273438880	-1121099408	-4280561376
33	1	33	561	6545	58905	435897	2760681	15380937	76904685	350343565	1471442973	5752004349
34	-1	-34	-595	-7140	-66045	-501942	-3262623	-18643560	-95548245	-445891810	-1917334783	-7669339132
35	1	35	630	7770	73815	575757	3838380	22481940	118030185	563921995	2481256778	10150595910
36	-1	-36	-666	-8436	-82251	-658008	-4496388	-26978328	-145008513	-708930508	-3190187286	-13340783196
37	1	37	703	9139	91390	749398	5245786	32224114	177232627	886163135	4076350421	17417133617
38	-1	-38	-741	-9880	-101270	-850668	-6096454	-38320568	-215553195	-1101716330	-5178066751	-22595200368
39	1	39	780	10660	111930	962598	7059052	45379620	260932815	1362649145	6540715896	29135916264
40	-1	-40	-820	-11480	-123410	-1086008	-8145060	-53524680	-314457495	-1677106640	-8217822536	-37353738800
41	1	41	861	12341	135751	1221759	9366819	62891499	377348994	2054455634	10272278170	47626016970
42	-1	-42	-903	-13244	-148995	-1370754	-10737573	-73629072	-450978066	-2505433700	-12777711870	-60403728840
43	1	43	946	14190	163185	1533939	12271512	85900584	536878650	3042312350	15820024220	76223753060
44	-1	-44	-990	-15180	-178365	-1712304	-13983816	-99884400	-636763050	-3679075400	-19499099620	-95722852680
45	1	45	1035	16215	194580	1906884	15890700	115775100	752538150	4431613550	23930713170	1.19654E+11
46	-1	-46	-1081	-17296	-211876	-2118760	-18009460	-133784560	-886322710	-5317936260	-29248649430	-1.48902E+11
47	1	47	1128	18424	230300	2349060	20358520	154143080	1040465790	6358402050	35607051480	1.84509E+11
48	-1	-48	-1176	-19600	-249900	-2598960	-22957480	-177100560	-1217566350	-7575968400	-43183019880	-2.27692E+11
49	1	49	1225	20825	270725	2869685	25827165	202927725	1420494075	8996462475	52179482355	2.79872E+11
50	-1	-50	-1275	-22100	-292825	-3162510	-28989675	-231917400	-1652411475	-10648873950	-62828356305	-3.427E+11

from one group to another. Also, from the Table 4, the maximum number of terms generated by any positive power of n can be known. The formula to determine the maximum number of terms generated by any positive power of n of a trinomial theorem is presented in the Kifilideen (2020) on the publication of development of Kifilideen trinomial theorem using matrix approach [11].

2.5. Kifilideen coefficient table for negative power of $-n$ of Kifilideen trinomial theorem based on matrix and standardized approach

Table 5 shows Kifilideen coefficient table for negative power of $-n$ of Kifilideen trinomial theorem based on matrix and standardized approach. The series of Kifilideen expansion of negative power of $-n$ of trinomial theorem gives infinite series which can be shown in the Table 5 below. From the Table 5; the change in colour from blue to red then to blue and so on to infinity for any particular negative power of $-n$ indicates the migration from one group to another. A clear study of Table 5 indicates that the coefficients of the negative power of -1 of Kifilideen trinomial theorem in periodicity and orderly manner can be generated from coefficients of Pascal triangle of binomial theorem of positive power of n . The coefficients of the negative power of -1 of Kifilideen trinomial theorem in orderly manner are $1; -1, -1; 1, 2, 1; -1, -3, -3, -1; 1, 4, 6, 4, 1; -1, -5, -10, -10, -5, -1; 1, 6, 15, 20, 15, 6, 1; \dots$

Also, the study of the Table 5 reveals that the coefficient of the negative power of -2 of Kifilideen trinomial theorem in periodicity and orderly manner can be generated from the coefficients of Pascal triangle of binomial theorem of positive power of n . The coefficients of the negative power of -2 of Kifilideen trinomial theorem in orderly manner are $1 (\times 1); -1, -1 (\times 2); 1, 2, 1 (\times 3); -1, -3, -3, -1 (\times 4); 1, 4, 6, 4, 1 (\times 5); -1, -5, -10, -10, -5, -1 (\times 6); 1, 6, 15, 20, 15, 6, 1 (\times 7); \dots$. So, the coefficients of the negative power of -2 of Kifilideen trinomial theorem in orderly manner are $1; -2, -2; 3, 6, 3; -4, -12, -12, -4; 5, 20, 30, 20, 5; -6, -30, -60, -60, -30, -6; 7, 42, 105, 140, 105, 42, 7; \dots$

2.6. Kifilideen theorem of matrix transformation of positive power of n of trinomial expression

If three variables x, y and z are found in each part of trinomial expression of positive power of n such as

$$\left[ux^a y^b z^c + vx^d y^e z^g + wx^h y^m z^p \right]^n \quad (1)$$

and the power combination of any term in the Kifilideen expansion of that kind of positive power of the trinomial expression is set as kif while the value of this term is designated as $qx^r y^s z^t$.

Then, the kifilideen matrix transformation of such positive power of n of the trinomial expression is of the form;

$$\begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} : \begin{bmatrix} a & d & h \\ b & e & m \\ c & g & p \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} k \\ i \\ f \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} r \\ s \\ t \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Thus $k + i + f = n$ and where u, v, w and q are constants

More so,

$${}_{kif}^{-n} C u^k v^i w^f = q \quad (3)$$

3. Results

3.1. Utilization of Kifilideen coefficient table for Kifilideen trinomial theorem based standardized and matrix approach

[i] Expand the following using Kifilideen coefficient table

$$[a] [x + y + z]^7 [b] \left(\frac{x^2}{y} - yz^3 + xz \right)^4 [c] (x + y + z)^{-5} [d] (1 + x + y)^{-3}$$

Solution

[a] From Kifilideen coefficient Table 3 for positive power of 7, the coefficientst in ascending order are 1,7,21,35,35, 21,7,1,7,42,105,140,105,42,7,21,105,210,210,105,21,35,140,210,105,21,35,140,210,140,35,105,105,35,21,42,21,7,7,1. So the expansion of $[x + y + z]^7$ using Kifilideen trinomial theorem based on standardized and matrix approach, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
[x + y + z]^7 &= 1 \times x^7 \times y^0 \times z^0 + 7 \times x^6 \times y^1 \times z^0 + 21 \times x^5 \times y^2 \times z^0 + 35 \times x^4 \times y^3 \times z^0 + 35 \times x^3 \times y^4 \times z^0 \\
&+ 21 \times x^2 \times y^5 \times z^0 + 7 \times x^1 \times y^6 \times z^0 + 1 \times x^0 \times y^7 \times z^0 + 7 \times x^6 \times y^0 \times z^1 + 42 \times x^5 \times y^1 \times z^1 + 105 \\
&\times x^4 \times y^2 \times z^1 + 140 \times x^3 \times y^3 \times z^1 + 105 \times x^2 \times y^4 \times z^1 + 42 \times x^1 \times y^5 \times z^1 + 7 \times x^0 \times y^6 \times z^1 \\
&+ 21 \times x^5 \times y^0 \times z^2 + 105 \times x^4 \times y^1 \times z^2 + 210 \times x^3 \times y^2 \times z^2 + 210 \times x^2 \times y^3 \times z^2 + 105 \times x^1 \times y^4 \times z^2 + 21 \times x^0 \times y^5 \times z^2 + 35 \\
&\times x^4 \times y^0 \times z^3 + 140 \times x^3 \times y^1 \times z^3 + 210 \times x^2 \times y^2 \times z^3 + 140 \times x^1 \times y^3 \times z^3 \\
&+ \times x^0 \times y^4 \times z^3 + 35 \times x^3 \times y^0 \times z^4 + 105 \times x^2 \times y^1 \times z^4 + 105 \times x^1 \times y^2 \times z^4 + 35 \times x^0 \times y^3 \times z^4 + 21 \times x^2 \times y^0 \times z^5 \\
&+ 42 \times x^1 \times y^1 \times z^5 + 21 \times x^0 \times y^2 \times z^5 + 7 \times x^1 \times y^0 \times z^6 + 7 \times x^0 \times y^1 \times z^6 + 1 \times x^0 \times y^0 \times z^7 \quad (4)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
[x + y + z]^7 &= x^7 + 7 x^6 y + 21 x^5 y^2 + 35 x^4 y^3 + 35 x^3 y^4 + 21 x^2 y^5 + 7 x y^6 + y^7 + 7 \times x^6 z + 42 x^5 y z + 105 x^4 y^2 z \\
&+ 140 x^3 y^3 z + 105 x^2 y^4 z + 42 x y^5 z + 7 y^6 z + 21 x^5 z^2 + 105 x^4 y z^2 + 210 x^3 y^2 z^2 + 210 x^2 y^3 z^2 + 105 x y^4 z^2 + 21 y^5 z^2 \\
&+ 35 x^4 z^3 + 140 x^3 y z^3 + 210 x^2 y^2 z^3 + 140 x y^3 z^3 + 35 y^4 z^3 + 35 x^3 z^4 + 105 x^2 y^1 z^4 + 105 x y^2 z^4 + 35 y^3 z^4 + 21 x^2 z^5 \\
&+ 42 x y z^5 + 21 y^2 z^5 + 7 x z^6 + 7 y z^6 + z^7 \quad (5)
\end{aligned}$$

[b] From Kifilideen coefficient Table 3 for positive power of 4, the coefficients in ascending order are 1,4,6,4,1,4,12,12,4,6,12,6,4,4,1. So the expansion of $\left(\frac{x^2}{y} - yz^3 + xz\right)^4$ using Kifilideen trinomial theorem of positive power of n based on standardized and matrix approach, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
(x^2 y^{-1} - yz^3 + xz)^4 &= 1 \times [x^2 y^{-1}]^4 [-yz^3]^0 [xz]^0 + 4 [x^2 y^{-1}]^3 [-yz^3]^1 [xz]^0 + 6 [x^2 y^{-1}]^2 [-yz^3]^2 [xz]^0 + \\
&+ 4 [x^2 y^{-1}]^1 [-yz^3]^3 [xz]^0 + [x^2 y^{-1}]^0 [-yz^3]^4 [xz]^0 + 4 [x^2 y^{-1}]^3 [-yz^3]^0 [xz]^1 + 12 [x^2 y^{-1}]^2 [-yz^3]^1 [xz]^1 \\
&+ 12 [x^2 y^{-1}]^1 [-yz^3]^2 [xz]^1 + 4 [x^2 y^{-1}]^0 [-yz^3]^3 [xz]^1 + 6 [x^2 y^{-1}]^3 [-yz^3]^0 [xz]^2 + 12 [x^2 y^{-1}]^2 [-yz^3]^1 [xz]^2 \\
&+ 6 [x^2 y^{-1}]^1 [-yz^3]^2 [xz]^2 + 4 [x^2 y^{-1}]^1 [-yz^3]^0 [xz]^3 + 4 [x^2 y^{-1}]^0 [-yz^3]^1 [xz]^3 + [x^2 y^{-1}]^0 [-yz^3]^0 [xz]^4 \quad (6)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
(x^2 y^{-1} - yz^3 + xz)^4 &= x^8 y^{-4} - 4x^6 y^{-2} z^3 + 6x^4 z^6 - 4x^2 y^2 z^9 + y^4 z^{12} + 4x^7 y^{-3} z - 12x^5 y^{-1} z^4 + 12x^3 y z^7 \\
&- 4x y^3 z^{10} + 6x^8 y^{-3} z^2 - 12x^4 y^{-1} z^5 + 6x^4 y z^8 + 4x^5 y^{-1} z^3 - 4x^3 y z^6 + x^4 z^4 \quad (7)
\end{aligned}$$

[c] From Kifilideen coefficient Table 4 for negative power of -5 , the coefficients in ascending order are 1, -5 , -5 , 15, 30, 15, -35 , -105 , -105 , -35 , 70, 280, 420, 280, 70, -126 , -630 , -1260 , -1260 , -630 , -126 ,

210, 1260, 3150, 4200, 3150, 1260, 210, – – – . The expansion gives infinite series. So the expansion of $(x + y + z)^{-5}$ using Kifilideen trinomial theorem of negative power of $-n$ based on standardized and matrix approach, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}(x + y + z)^{-5} = & x^{-5}y^0z^0 - 5x^{-6}y^1z^0 - 5x^{-6}y^0z^1 + 15x^{-7}y^2z^0 + 30x^{-7}y^1z^1 + 15x^{-7}y^0z^2 - 35x^{-8}y^3z^0 - \\ & 105x^{-8}y^2z^1 - 105x^{-8}y^1z^2 - 35x^{-8}y^0z^3 + 70x^{-9}y^4z^0 + 280x^{-9}y^3z^1 + 420x^{-9}y^2z^2 + 280x^{-9}y^1z^3 \\ & + 70x^{-9}y^0z^4 - 126x^{-10}y^5z^0 - 630x^{-10}y^4z^1 - 1260x^{-10}y^3z^2 - 1260x^{-10}y^2z^3 - 630x^{-10}y^1z^4 - 126x^{-10}y^0z^5 \\ & + 210x^{-11}y^6z^0 + 1260x^{-10}y^5z^1 + 3150x^{-10}y^4z^2 + 4200x^{-10}y^3z^3 + 3150x^{-10}y^2z^4 + 1260x^{-10}y^1z^5 + 210x^{-11}y^0z^6\end{aligned}$$

[d] From Kifilideen coefficient table 4 for negative power of -3 , the coefficients in ascending order are 1, -3 , -3 , 6, 12, 6, -10 , -30 , -30 , -10 , 15, 60, 90, 60, 15, -21 , -105 , -210 , -210 , -105 , -21 , 28, 168, 420, 560, 420, 168, 28, – – –. The expansion gives infinite series. So the expansion of $(1 + y + z)^{-3}$ using Kifilideen trinomial theorem of negative power of $-n$ based on standardized and matrix approach, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}(1 + x + y)^{-3} = & 1 - 3x^1y^0 - 3x^0y^1 + 6x^2y^0 + 12x^1y^1 + 6x^0y^2 - 10x^3y^0 - 30x^2y^1 - 30x^1y^2 - 10x^0y^3 \\ & + 15x^4y^0 + 60x^3y^1 + 90x^2y^2 + 60x^1y^3 + 15x^0y^4 - 21y^5z^0 - 105y^4z^1 - 210y^3z^2 - 210y^2z^3 - 105y^1z^4 \\ & - 21y^0z^5 + 28y^6z^0 + 168y^5z^1 + 420y^4z^2 + 560y^3z^3 + 420y^2z^4 + 168y^1z^5 + 28y^0z^6 + \dots\end{aligned}\quad (8)$$

[ii] Expand the trinomial expression $[x + y + z]^{-1}$ using Kifilideen trinomial theorem for negative power of $-n$ based on standardized and matrix approach. Obtain the coefficients of the series using Kifilideen coefficient table. Hence or otherwise generate the series of $\frac{35}{82}$ (Hint: take $x = 2$, $y = \frac{1}{5}$ and $z = \frac{1}{7}$)

Solution

From Kifilideen coefficient Table 4 for negative power of -1 , the coefficients in ascending order are 1, -1 , -1 , 1, 2, 1, -1 , -3 , -3 , -1 , 1, 4, 6, 4, 1, -1 , -5 , -10 , -10 , -5 , -1 , 1, 6, 15, 20, 15, 6, 1, -7 , -21 , -35 , -35 , ... The expansion gives infinite series. So the expansion of $(1 + y + z)^{-3}$ using Kifilideen trinomial theorem of negative power of $-n$ based on standardized and matrix approach, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}[x + y + z]^{-1} = & x^{-1}y^0z^0 - x^{-2}y^1z^0 - x^{-2}y^0z^1 + x^{-3}y^2z^0 + 2x^{-3}y^1z^1 + x^{-3}y^0z^2 - x^{-4}y^3z^0 - 3x^{-4}y^2z^1 \\ & - 3x^{-4}y^1z^2 - x^{-4}y^0z^3 + x^{-5}y^4z^0 + 4x^{-5}y^3z^1 + 6x^{-5}y^2z^2 + 4x^{-5}y^1z^3 + x^{-5}y^0z^4 - x^{-6}y^5z^0 - 5x^{-6}y^4z^1 \\ & - 10x^{-6}y^3z^2 - 10x^{-6}y^2z^3 - 5x^{-6}y^1z^4 - x^{-6}y^0z^5 + x^{-7}y^6z^0 + 6x^{-7}y^5z^1 + 15x^{-7}y^4z^2 + 20x^{-7}y^3z^3 + 15x^{-7}y^2z^4 \\ & + 6x^{-7}y^1z^5 + x^{-7}y^0z^6 - x^{-8}y^7z^0 - 7x^{-8}y^6z^1 - 21x^{-8}y^5z^2 - 35x^{-8}y^4z^3 - 35x^{-8}y^3z^4 - 21x^{-8}y^2z^5 - 7x^{-8}y^1z^6 \\ & - x^{-8}y^0z^7 + \dots\end{aligned}\quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned}[x + y + z]^{-1} = & x^{-1} - x^{-2}y - x^{-2}z + x^{-3}y^2 + 2x^{-3}yz + x^{-3}z^2 - x^{-4}y^3 - 3x^{-4}y^2z - 3x^{-4}yz^2 - x^{-4}z^3 \\ & + x^{-5}y^4 + 4x^{-5}y^3z + 6x^{-5}y^2z^2 + 4x^{-5}yz^3 + x^{-5}z^4 - x^{-6}y^5 - 5x^{-6}y^4z - 10x^{-6}y^3z^2 - 10x^{-6}y^2z^3 - 5x^{-6}z^4 \\ & - x^{-6}z^5 + 6x^{-7}y^5z + 15x^{-7}y^4z^2 + 20x^{-7}y^3z^3 + 15x^{-7}y^2z^4 + 6x^{-7}yz^5 + x^{-7}z^6 - x^{-8}y^7 - 7x^{-8}y^6z^1 \\ & - 21x^{-8}y^5z^2 - 35x^{-8}y^4z^3 - 35x^{-8}y^3z^4 - 21x^{-8}y^2z^5 - 7x^{-8}yz^6 - x^{-8}z^7 + \dots\end{aligned}\quad (10)$$

$$[b] \frac{35}{82} = \left[2 + \frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{7}\right]^{-1}$$

Using the Kifilideen expansion above where $x = 2$, $y = \frac{1}{5}$ and $z = \frac{1}{7}$, we have:

$$\frac{35}{82} = \left[2 + \frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{7}\right]^{-1} = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{4 \times 5} - \frac{1}{4 \times 7} + \frac{1}{8 \times 25} + \frac{2}{8 \times 5 \times 7} + \frac{1}{8 \times 49} - \frac{1}{16 \times 125} - \frac{3}{16 \times 25 \times 7} - \frac{3}{16 \times 5 \times 49}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -\frac{1}{16 \times 343} + \frac{1}{32 \times 625} + \frac{4}{32 \times 125 \times 7} + \frac{6}{32 \times 25 \times 49} + \frac{4}{32 \times 5 \times 343} + \frac{1}{32 \times 2401} - \frac{1}{64 \times 3125} - \frac{5}{64 \times 625 \times 7} \\
& -\frac{10}{64 \times 125 \times 49} - \frac{10}{64 \times 25 \times 343} - \frac{5}{64 \times 5 \times 2401} - \frac{1}{64 \times 16807} + \frac{1}{128 \times 15625} + \frac{6}{128 \times 3125 \times 7} + \frac{15}{128 \times 625 \times 49} \\
& + \frac{20}{128 \times 125 \times 343} + \frac{15}{128 \times 25 \times 2401} + \frac{6}{128 \times 5 \times 16807} + \frac{1}{128 \times 117649} - \frac{1}{256 \times 78125} - \frac{7}{256 \times 15625 \times 7} \\
& -\frac{21}{256 \times 3125 \times 49} - \frac{35}{256 \times 625 \times 343} - \frac{35}{256 \times 125 \times 2401} - \frac{21}{256 \times 25 \times 16807} - \frac{7}{256 \times 5 \times 117649} - \frac{1}{256 \times 823543} \dots
\end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

The evaluation of the above series gives 0.426829 to 6 decimal places. Also, using calculator $\frac{35}{82}$ gives 0.426829 to 6 decimal places. This indicates that the negative power of -1 of Kifilideen trinomial theorem and coefficient of negative power of -1 from the Kifilideen Coefficient table are valid.

[iii] Expand the trinomial expression $[x + y + z]^3$ using Kifilideen trinomial theorem for positive power of n based on standardized and matrix approach. Obtain the coefficients of the series using Kifilideen coefficient table. Hence or otherwise generate the series of $[3.74]^3$ and evaluate its value (Hint: take $x = 3$, $y = 0.7$ or $\frac{7}{10}$ and $z = 0.04$ or $\frac{4}{100}$).

Solution

[a] From Kifilideen coefficient Table 3 for positive power of 3, the coefficients in ascending order are 1, 3, 3, 1, 3, 6, 3, 3, 3, 1. So the expansion of $[x + y + z]^3$ using Kifilideen trinomial theorem based on standardized and matrix approach, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
[x + y + z]^3 = & x^3y^0z^0 + 3x^2y^1z^0 + 3x^1y^2z^0 + x^0y^3z^0 + 3x^2y^0z^1 + 6x^1y^1z^1 + 3x^0y^2z^1 + 3x^1y^0z^2 + 3x^0y^1z^2 \\
& + x^0y^0z^3
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

$$[x + y + z]^3 = x^3 + 3x^2y + 3xy^2 + y^3 + 3x^2z + 6xyz + 3y^2z + 3xz^2 + 3yz^2 + z^3 \tag{13}$$

$$\text{[b] } [3.74]^3 = \left[3 + \frac{7}{10} + \frac{4}{100}\right]^3$$

Using the kif expansion above where $x = 3$, $y = \frac{7}{10}$ and $z = \frac{4}{100}$, we have

$$[3.74]^3 = \left[3 + \frac{7}{10} + \frac{4}{100}\right]^3 = 27 + \frac{189}{10} + \frac{441}{100} + \frac{343}{1000} + \frac{108}{100} + \frac{504}{1000} + \frac{588}{10000} + \frac{144}{10000} + \frac{336}{100000} + \frac{64}{1000000} \tag{14}$$

$$[3.74]^3 = 27 + 18.9 + 4.41 + 0.343 + 1.08 + 0.504 + 0.0588 + 0.0144 + 0.00336 + 0.000064 \tag{15}$$

$$[3.74]^3 = 52.313624 \tag{16}$$

From calculator, the value of $[3.74]^3$ is also 52.313624. This indicates that the positive power of 3 of Kifilideen trinomial theorem and coefficient of positive power of 3 of trinomial expression from the Kifilideen Coefficient table are valid.

[iv] Determine the power combination of the Kifilideen expansion of negative power of -3 in the row 13 and column 10 of the Kif matrix of the Kifilideen expansion $[x + y + z]^{-3}$. Hence or otherwise determine the term the generate the power combination and using Kifilideen coefficient table of negative power of $-n$ of trinomial theorem determine the coefficient of the power combination.

Solution

[a] From the question, $n = -3$, $r = 13$ and $c = 10$

Using Kifilideen General Row Column Matrix formula for negative power of $-n$ [12],

$$CP_{rc} = n00 - 110(r - 1) + 9(r - c) \quad (17)$$

$$CP_{rc} = -300 - 110(13 - 1) + 9(13 - 10) \quad (18)$$

$$CP_{rc} = -1593 \quad (19)$$

[b] From Kifilideen General Term formula for negative power of $-n$ [12],

$$t = \frac{[n - k]^2 + [n - k] + 2f + 2}{2}$$

Where,

t – the required t^{th} term

k – the first component part of the power combination

i – the second component part of the power combination

f – the third component part of the power combination

n – the negative power of $-n$ of the trinomial expression

From, $CP_{rc} = -1593$, $k = -15$, $i = 9$ and $f = 3$

$$t = \frac{[-3 - -15]^2 + [-3 - -15] + 2 \times 3 + 2}{2}$$

$t = 82^{th}$ term

Using the Kifilideen Coefficient table of negative power of -3 ,

The coefficient of $CP_{rc} = -1593$ of term 82^{th} term is $+20020$.

3.2. Demonstration on the implementation of Kifilideen theorem of matrix transformation of positive power of n of trinomial expression

Given that a term in the Kifilideen expansion of $\left[\frac{y^3}{4x^2z^5} - \frac{x^7z^4}{2y} + \frac{ey^6z^8}{x} \right]^n$ is $\frac{-1575}{2048} x^{26} y^{13} z^8$ where e is a constant value. Using Kifilideen matrix transformation method of positive power of n of trinomial expression. Find

[i] the power combination

[ii] the degree of the positive power of the trinomial expression

[iii] the t^{th} term

[iv] the value of e .

Solution

[i] Trinomial expression: $\left[4^{-1}x^{-2}y^3z^{-5} - 2^{-1}x^7y^{-1}z^4 + ex^{-1}y^6z^8 \right]^n$

Power combination to be obtained: $k \quad i \quad f$

t^{th} term of the power combination: $\frac{-1575}{2048} x^{26} y^{13} z^8$

Using the kifilideen matrix transformation method, so

$$\begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} : \begin{bmatrix} -2 & 7 & -1 \\ 3 & -1 & 6 \\ -5 & 4 & 8 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} k \\ i \\ f \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 26 \\ 13 \\ 8 \end{bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

Also, $k + i + f = n$

Using Cramer's rule, so

$$k = \frac{\Delta k}{\Delta} = \frac{\begin{vmatrix} 26 & 7 & -1 \\ 13 & -1 & 6 \\ 8 & 4 & 8 \end{vmatrix}}{\begin{vmatrix} -2 & 7 & -1 \\ 3 & -1 & 6 \\ -5 & 4 & 8 \end{vmatrix}}$$

$$k = \frac{-1284}{-321} \quad (21)$$

$$k = 4 \quad (22)$$

$$i = \frac{\Delta i}{\Delta} = \frac{\begin{vmatrix} -2 & 26 & -1 \\ 3 & 13 & 6 \\ -5 & 8 & 8 \end{vmatrix}}{\begin{vmatrix} -2 & 7 & -1 \\ 3 & -1 & 6 \\ -5 & 4 & 8 \end{vmatrix}}$$

$$i = \frac{-1605}{-321} \quad (23)$$

$$i = 5 \quad (24)$$

$$f = \frac{\Delta f}{\Delta} = \frac{\begin{vmatrix} -2 & 7 & 26 \\ 3 & -1 & 13 \\ -5 & 4 & 8 \end{vmatrix}}{\begin{vmatrix} -2 & 7 & -1 \\ 3 & -1 & 6 \\ -5 & 4 & 8 \end{vmatrix}}$$

$$f = \frac{-321}{-321} \quad (25)$$

$$f = 1 \quad (26)$$

So, the power combination = $kif = 451$

[ii] the positive power of n of the trinomial expression = $n = k + i + f = 4 + 5 + 1$

$$n = 10 \quad (27)$$

[iii] $C_p = kif = 451$

$$k = 4, i = 5 \text{ and } f = 1 \quad (28)$$

$$n = k + i + f = 4 + 5 + 1 = 10 \quad (29)$$

From Kifilideen general term formula [19],

$$t = \frac{-f^2 + 2fn + 3f + 2i + 2}{2}$$

Where,

C_p – the given power combination

k, i, f – the component parts of the power combination

f – the third component part of the given power combination

i – the second component part of the given power combination

n – the degree of the positive power of the trinomial expression

t – the term of the given power combination to be determined

$$t = \frac{-[1]^2 + 2 \times 1 \times 10 + 3 \times 1 + 2 \times 5 + 2}{2}$$

$$t = 17^{\text{th}} \text{ term}$$

OR

Using Kifilideen general power combination formula [11,20,21],

$$C_p = kif = 451 \quad (30)$$

$$k = 4, i = 5 \text{ and } f = 1 \quad (31)$$

$$n = k + i + f = 4 + 5 + 1 = 10 \quad (32)$$

$$a = f = 1 \quad (33)$$

$$m = \frac{a}{2} [2n - a - 1] = \frac{1}{2} [2 \times 10 - 1 - 1] = 9 \quad (34)$$

$$C_p = kif = -90t + 81a + 90m + n90$$

Where,

C_p – Power combination, kif

t - nth term of the kifilideen trinomial theorem

a - the power of the third digit, f of the power combination or the value of the third digit of the column or group the term fall into

a and m - are constant values for a particular group or column of the matrix

n - the power of the trinomial expression

k, i and f – the first, second and third component part of the power combination

$$451 = kif = 90t + 81 \times 1 + 90 \times 9 + 1090$$

$t = 17^{th}$ term

OR

Using alternate Kifilideen general power combination formula [19],

From the question, $C_p = kif = 451$

$$k = 4, i = 5, f = 1 \text{ and } n = 10$$

$$C_p = kif = 90t - 45f^2 + 36f + 90fn + n90$$

$$451 = -90t - 45[1]^2 + 36 \times 1 + 90 \times 1 \times 10 + 1090$$

$t = 17^{th}$ term

[iv] From the question, $u = 4, v = 1, w = e$ and $q = \frac{-1575}{2048}$

Using Kifilideen matrix transformation method,

$${}_{kif}^n C u^k v^i w^f = q \quad (35)$$

$${}_{451}^{10} C [4^{-1}]^4 [-2^{-1}]^5 [e]^1 = \frac{-1575}{2048} \quad (36)$$

From the Kifilideen coefficient table, the coefficient of the 17^{th} term on the $n = 10$ column is 1260

$$1260 \times \frac{1}{256} \times -\frac{1}{32} \times e = \frac{-1575}{2048} \quad (37)$$

$$e = 5 \quad (38)$$

4. Conclusion

Kifilideen theorem of matrix transformation of positive power of n of trinomial expression in which three variables x, y and z are found in parts of the trinomial expression was established. The research work established Kifilideen coefficient tables for positive and negative powers of n and $-n$ of Kifilideen trinomial theorem base on standardized and matrix approach. The development of theorem of matrix transformation of positive power of n of trinomial expression would make the process of evaluating such positive power of n of the trinomial expression easy. The inaugurated tables had been fully utilized to generate series of expansion for positive and negative power of binomial and trinomial expressions. The Kifilideen coefficient tables are handy and effective in generating the coefficients of terms and series of the Kifilideen expansion of trinomial expression of powers of n and $-n$.

References

- [1] Goss, D. (2011). The Ongoing Binomial Revolution. Number Theory, Spring.
- [2] Aljohani, S. (2016). History of Binomial Theory. *International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*, 7(4), 161 - 162.
- [3] Malhotra, O. P., Gupta, S. K., & Gangal, A. *ISC Maths XI*. S. Chand Publishing.

- [4] Guicciardini, N. (2012). John Wallis as editor of Newton's mathematical work. *Notes and Records of the Royal Society*, 66(1), 3-17.
- [5] Bogomolny, A. (2018). *Treatise on Arithmetical Triangle*. Cut the Knot, Wolfram Technology, New Brunswick, New Jersey, United States.
- [6] Leavitt, S. (2011). *The Simple Complexity of Pascal's Triangle*. Master Project, Department of Mathematics, PennState College of Information Science and Technology, Westgate Building, University Park, Pennsylvania, United States.
- [7] Brothers, H. J. (2012). 96.20 Pascal's triangle: The hidden store. *The Mathematical Gazette*, 96(535), 145-148.
- [8] Hosch, W. L., & Chauhan, Y. (2013). *Pascal's Triangle*. Britannica, Chicago, Illinois, U.S., 30 pages.
- [9] Lodder, J. (2017). Pascal's Triangle and Mathematical Induction. *Number Theory*, 5, 1-26.
- [10] James, L. T. (2019). Analogues Between Leibniz's Harmonic Triangle and Pascal's Arithmetic Triangle.
- [11] Osanyinpeju, K. L. (2020a). Development of Kifilideen Trinomial Theorem Using Matrix Approach. *International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology*, 7(7), 117-135.
- [12] Osanyinpeju K.L. (2021a). Inauguration of Negative Power of - n of Kifilideen Trinomial Theorem using Standardized and Matrix Methods. 2nd International Conference on Engineering and Environmental Sciences (ICEES) Theme: Re - Thinking Engineering and Technology for Engineering Sustainability in the Face of Global Pandemic 23rd - 25th November 2021 12 pg.
- [13] Osanyinpeju, K. L. (2021b). Inauguration of Negative Power of - n of Kifilideen Trinomial Theorem using Standardized and Matrix Methods. *Acta Electronica Malaysia*, 5(1), 17-23.
- [14] Osanyinpeju, K. L. (2022). Four and Five Figures of Kifilideen (Power of Base 11) and Antikifilideen (Antipower of BASE 11) Tables as a Tool for Mathematics Computation. *Momona Ethiopian Journal of Science*, 14(2), 178-196.
- [15] Osanyinpeju, K. L. (2019, November). Development of Kifilideen (Power of Base 11) and Antikifilideen (Antipower of Base 11) Tables. In *1st International Conference on Engineering and Environmental Sciences (ICEES) Theme: Advancing Technology and Environment Burdens (Challenges and Sustainable Solution 5th-7th November 2019 pg 957-968*.
- [16] Osanyinpeju, K. L. (2020). Computation of the power of base of two digits number using Kifilideen (Matrix, Combination and Distributive (MCD)) approach. *Matrix Science Mathematics*, 4(1), 14-19.
- [17] Osanyinpeju, K. L. (2020). Development of Kifilideen (Power of Base 11), Antikifilideen (Antipower of Base 11) and Other Tables. *Eliva Press SRL Publisher, MD-2060, bd. Cuza-Voda, 1/4, of, 21*, 136.
- [18] Osanyinpeju, K. L. (2020). Utilization of Kifilideen Trinomial Theorem based on Matrix Approach in Computation of the Power of Base of Tri-Digits Number. In *International Conference on Electrical Engineering Applications (ICEEA'2020), Department of Electrical Engineering, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria. 23rd-25th (pp. 192-199)*.
- [19] Osanyinpeju K.L. (2021c). Invention of the Kifilideen General Term Formula of Positive Power of n of Kifilideen Trinomial Theorem based on Standardized and matrix methods with other Establishments. Federal University of Agriculture Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria 12 pg.
- [20] Osanyinpeju, K. L. (2021, November). Application of Expansion of Negative Power of -n of Kifilideen Trinomial Theorem for the Transformation of Compound Fraction into Series of Partial Fraction with Other Developments (Paper Presentation). In *2nd International Conference on Engineering and Environmental Sciences (ICEES), Osun State University. Theme: Re-thinking Engineering and Technology for Engineering Sustainability in the Face of Global Pandemic (pp. 23-25)*.
- [21] Osanyinpeju, K. L. (2020, July). Development of Kifilideen Trinomial Theorem Using Matrix Approach. In *International Conference on Electrical Engineering Applications (ICEEA 2020), Department of Electrical Engineering, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Kaduna State, Nigeria. (Vol. 5792353)*.

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